

معوقات مكاتب الخدمة الاجتماعية بإدارة حماية الأسرة في الأردن من وجهة نظر بعض موظفيها ونظرائهم المعنيين بشأنها الفني

Obstacles Facing Social Services Offices at Family Protection Department in Jordan from the View- point of Some Employees and Those Concerned with Their Technical Affairs

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والاعتراف الرسمي بصعوبة عملهم التي يمكن الوفاء بها وبغيرها في حال تطوير موارد وزارتهم.

ملخص:

استهدفت الدراسة الإجابة عن سؤالها الرئيس القائل: ما معوقات مكاتب الخدمة الاجتماعية بإدارة حماية الأسرة في الأردن وأنماط متلقي خدماتها واحتياجات كوادرها من وجهة نظر بعض موظفيها ونظرائهم المعنيين بشأنها الفني من ملاك وزارة التنمية الاجتماعية؟، من خلال استعمالها لمنهج البحث النوعي القائم على أربع طرق، هي: تحليل مضمون؛ للوقوف على دور المكاتب المبحوثة ومهامها وخصائص متلقي خدماتها، المقابلات شبه المقننة مع بعض موظفي المكاتب والمعنيين بشأنها الفني؛ لتحديد معوقات وأثر نمط متلقي خدماتها في تطوير معارف ومهارات واتجاهات موظفيها، العصف الذهني؛ لتبيان الاحتياجات التدريبية لموظفي المكاتب المدروسة وامنياتهم، ومجموعات العمل البؤرية المؤلفة من بعض موظفي المكاتب المبحوثة والمعنيين بشأنها الفني؛ لتحديد سبل التغلب على تحدياتها. واستوفت الدراسة بياناتها ومعلوماتها من عينة قصدية من الموظفين، قوامها 11 موظفاً وموظفة من موظفي مكاتب الخدمة الاجتماعية والمعنيين بشأنها الفني، يتوزعون على فئتين، الأولى تشمل ثمانية رؤساء لمكاتب الخدمة الاجتماعية، شكلوا ما نسبته 47% من مجموع رؤساء المكاتب البالغ عددهم (17) رئيساً، وما نسبته 18% من مجموع الموظفين العاملين في المكاتب البالغ عددهم (45) موظفاً وموظفة. أما الفئة الثانية فهي تشمل على ثلاثة موظفين من مركز وزارة التنمية الاجتماعية وميدانها.

وأظهرت نتائج الدراسة أن مكاتب الخدمة الاجتماعية بإدارة حماية الأسرة وأقسامها تواجه (20) معوقاً أهمها غموض الدور المهني للعاملين الاجتماعيين فيها وتهميشهم من قبل ضباط الشرطة وضياع مرجعيتهم الفنية ما بين بعض مديريات وزارتهم وتداخل حدود سلطاتهم ومسؤولياتهم مع نظرائهم الشرطيين وكثرة الملفات المطلوب متابعتها من قبلهم وغياب بطاقات وصف وظائفهم وانعدام ادلتهم الاجرائية، يمكن معالجتها جمعياً بنهج الاعتماد المؤسسي وضبط جودة الخدمات. كما اظهرت النتائج أيضاً بأن أكثر الفئات المتلقية لخدمات مكاتب الخدمة الاجتماعية، هي فئتي ضحايا العنف الجنسي والجسدي، اللتين تطلبا من مقدمي الخدمات لهما تطوير معارفهم ومهاراتهم واتجاهاتهم. كذلك بينت النتائج وجود ثمانية احتياجات تدريبية لموظفي مكاتب الخدمة الاجتماعية جاء في مقدمتها تطبيقات التشريعات الحمائية الاجتماعية التي يمكن تلبيتها من خلال برامج التعليم المستمر، وسبعة توقعات لهؤلاء الموظفين من السلطة المشرفة عليهم أهمها حصولهم على الحوافز المالية

الكلمات المفتاحية: إدارة حماية الأسرة، مكاتب الخدمة الاجتماعية، متلقي خدمات مكاتب الخدمة الاجتماعية، مقدمي الخدمات في مكاتب الخدمة الاجتماعية.

Abstract:

This study aims at answering the questions: What are the obstacles facing social services offices at the Family Protection Department in Jordan? What are the patterns of beneficiaries receiving services? What are the requirements and aspirations of staff from the viewpoint of employees and those concerned with technical affairs?

The study used the qualitative research method based on four approaches: Content analysis to examine the roles, tasks and features of the service recipients of the examined offices. Semi-structured interviews with some of the office employees and those concerned with their technical affairs to determine obstacles facing them and the impact of the service recipients' trends on the development of the employees' knowledge, skills and trends. Brainstorming to determine the training requirements and aspirations of the employees. Focus groups conducted with some of the employees and those concerned with their technical affairs to determine methods used to overcome their obstacles. The study received its data and information from a deliberate sample of employees consisting of 11 male and female employees of social services offices and those concerned with their technical affairs. They are divided into two groups. The first group consists of eight heads of social services offices comprising 47% of all heads of offices, consisting of 17% and 18% of the total number of employees working in the offices, which are 45 male and female employees. The second group consists of three employees from the Ministry of Social Development's headquarters and field offices.

The study results revealed that social services offices of the Family Protection Department face twenty obstacles. The most significant of which were: the unclear professional role carried out by social workers at those offices, their marginalization by police officers, the loss of technical reference among their ministry's directorates, the overlap of their authorities and tasks with their police counterparts, the many files

they are required to follow up on, the absence of employment description cards and the lack of procedural manuals. These problems can be treated collectively by adopting an institutional trend and quality control of services. Results also revealed that the sectors receiving most of the services from social services offices are victims of both sexual and physical violence. This demands that service providers for these sectors develop their knowledge, skills and trends. The results also revealed that employees of social services offices have eight training requirements, the most important of which are the implementation of social protection legislations, which can be met through continuous education programs. These workers also have seven expectations from the ministry supervising them, the most important of which are receiving financial incentives and officially recognizing the difficulty of their jobs. These expectations and others can be met should their ministry's resources be developed.

Keywords: Family Protection Department, Social Services Offices, Social Services Offices Recipients, Social Services Offices Providers.

Introduction

The family enjoys large significance in the Jordanian society due to its largely effective social role. Its importance and ways to protect its entity, strengthen its bonds and consolidate its values were mentioned clearly in Jordanian national documents. For example, the Jordanian Constitution in item 4 of article 6 stated that "the family is the foundation of society and is based on religion, morals and love of the homeland. The law preserves its legal status and empowers its bonds and values" (Prime Ministry, 2015). The Jordanian National Charter of 1990 also stressed the need for the state to provide motives for family formation and dignified life. The "We are All Jordan Initiative 2006" also called for promoting the rights of children and women through integrating their national frameworks with their international counterparts which have been ratified, signed or joined by Jordan (Jordan National Council for Family Affairs, p 2).

Jordan's 2025 Vision (2015) on society also suggested a group of initiatives related to family development such as care for the elderly and enhancement of the role of the family through improvement of fatherhood and motherhood and widening the scope of participation of guardians in education (Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation, 2015).

Despite the importance of the family institution in Jordanian society, its functions were reduced to two main aspects: (1) Having children, raising and caring for them; and (2) Debriefing the charged emotions of their members (Al Zaghhal, 1989). Recently, families are facing the challenges of various types of violence such as physical, sexual, psychological and neglect. This violence usually targets the more vulnerable members of a family such as children, women, the handicapped and the elderly, as has been revealed by the field studies, and as will be further explained in this study.

Because of the challenge of family violence in the Jordanian society, efforts to confront it began in 1997. These efforts witnessed the Public Security Department establishing the Family Protection Division at the Shmeisani police station, which was later promoted to a department now known as the Family Protection Department. This department has its headquarters in Amman governorate and has divisions in other Jordanian governorates. It operates in partnership with the ministries of National Development and Health and includes in its divisions 17 social services offices (Ministry of Social Development, 2016)

This study is geared towards diagnosing, evaluating and revising the Family Protection Department's seventeen social services offices dispersed throughout the governorates. The study is the result of the complaints reported by some of those offices' workers on the obstacles they face during work, the difficulties of some cases they deal with and the failure to respond to their training requirements, which they circulate in their professional forums.

The remaining part of the study consists of three parts. The first is an introductory one and consists of two branches: the study introductions consisting of its justifications, importance, objectives, problem, methodology and previous studies. The second is theoretical and includes the scientific justification of the occurrence of family violence and its effect on the roles of social specialists and on the formation and development of the protection system against family violence in Jordan and on the rates and trends of family protection cases in Jordan from a statistical perspective. The second part reveals the study results, conclusions, recommendations and suggestions.

Study Introductions

1. *Study Justifications, Importance, Objectives and Problem:*

◆ **Study Justifications:**

- The absence of any previous study dealing with the issue of obstacles facing social services offices at the Family Protection Department and the requirements of their employees. This is a pioneering study in this area in its capacity as a visualization of the perceptions of social workers using the qualitative research method.
- Estimating the training requirements of social workers at social services offices connected to the Family Protection Department to suggest what is needed to meet these requirements.
- Determining the aspirations of the social workers at the social services offices at the Department in the aim of explaining them to their administrative reference (Ministry of Social Development).

◆ **Study Importance:**

The importance of this study stems from its expected outputs (answers to its questions) which should help, should they be adopted by those concerned, to provide feedback to social safety development initiatives stipulated in the Jordan Vision 2025 (Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation, 2015), to develop the National Framework for Family Protection against Violence (National Council for Women's Affairs, 2016) and to achieve the objectives of the Ministry of Social Development's Strategic Plan for the period 2017- 2021 regarding the development of human resources (Ministry of Social Development, 2017).

◆ **Study Objectives:**

The study has two types of objectives. The first is a general one and is concerned with determining the obstacles facing social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions in Jordan, the trends of their service recipients and the requirements and aspirations of their workers from the point of view of some of their employees and those concerned with their technical affairs including officials at the Ministry of Social Development. The second type of objectives is specific and is related to the following:

- Revealing the obstacles facing social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions in Jordan from the point of view of some of their employees and those concerned with their technical affairs including officials at the Ministry of Social Development.

- Determining the trends of recipients of services of social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions in Jordan from the point of view of some of their employees and those concerned with their technical affairs such as officials at the Ministry of Social Development.
- Determining the training requirements of workers at social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions in Jordan from the point of view of some of the workers and some of those concerned with their technical affairs such as officials at the Ministry of Development.
- Revealing the aspirations of employees working at social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions in Jordan from the point of view of some of the workers and those concerned with their technical affairs such as officials at the Ministry of Social Development.

◆ **Study Problem:**

Following the Jordanian Public Security Directorate establishing a headquarters for the Family Protection Department and divisions in governorates in 1997, a partnership agreement was signed between the directorate and the Ministry of Social Development in 1998. This agreement resulted in the establishment of 17 social services offices for the department including 45 male and female social workers whose work involves providing social services to victims of family violence. The average annual number of such cases during the period between 1998 and 2015 amounted to 3903.83 and cases that followed up between 2007 and 2017 had an annual average of 4730.27.

As social workers working at social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions showed negative and pessimistic attitudes towards their work, as revealed by Ratrout (2009) study, and as their workloads while following up cases were very large as revealed by a report by the Ministry of Social Development (2017), and as their professional roles within the partnership methodology is vague according to the data provided by the National Framework for Family Protection against Violence (National Council for Family Affairs, 2016), this study comes to investigate the obstacles facing their offices' operations and the trends of service recipients. It also aims at estimating their requirements and determining their aspirations from the point of

view of some of them and from the point of view of some of those responsible for their technical affairs such as officials at the Ministry of Social Development. In other words, this study came to answer its main question and sub-questions.

The study's main question is: What are the obstacles facing social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions in Jordan? What are the trends of their service recipients and the requirements and aspirations of their staff from the viewpoint of some of their employees and those concerned with their technical affairs from the Ministry of Social Development? The questions branching from the study's main question are as follows:

- What are the obstacles facing social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions in Jordan from the viewpoint of some of their employees and those concerned with their technical affairs from the Ministry of Social Development?
- What are the trends of service recipients of social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions in Jordan from the viewpoint of some of their employees and those concerned with their technical affairs from the Ministry of Social Development?
- What are training requirements of employees of social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions in Jordan from the viewpoint of some of their employees and those concerned with their technical affairs from the Ministry of Social Development?
- What are the aspirations of social services offices employees at the Family Protection Department and its divisions in Jordan from the viewpoint of some of their employees and those concerned with their technical affairs from the Ministry of Social Development?

The study has some pivotal terms, which are listed below with the procedural definition of each:

- Family Protection Department: A department established by the Public Security Directorate in 1997 to deal with issued of family violence by receiving reports of such incidents, carrying out investigations into them, referring them to concerned bodies and following up victims.
- Social Services Offices: They are offices established by the Ministry of Social

Development as part of the Family Protection Department pursuant to a partnership agreement signed with the Public Security Directorate to carry out social case studies on family violence victims and provide them and their families with social services.

- Social Services Offices Recipients: They are victims of family violence who seek the help of the Family Protection Department. Their case studies reveal their need for social services, which they receive through the Ministry of Social Development and the National Aid Fund.
- Service Providers at the Social Services Offices: They are the employees appointed by the Minister of Social Services at the social services offices to carry out social case studies on family violence victims and provide the social services needed by those victims.

Data and information obtained from the respondents were processed according to two methods: the first was qualitative and relied on consensus or relative compatibility according to the "Delphi Technique" well-known among users of qualitative research, and the second was quantitative and was reflected by some descriptive statistical coefficients represented by crude rates and modes.

2. Previous Studies

The Family Protection Department's work was accompanied with conducting many field studies aiming at understanding or evaluating the outcomes of institutional efforts to intervene in such cases.

◆ ***The most recent studies conducted to understand family violence in the Jordanian Society are as follows:***

- The National Council for Family Affairs study (2013) on the social and economic characteristics of family violence cases dealt with by the Family Protection Department during 2009. This study resulted in a group of outcomes such as that physical abuse was the most practiced form of violence at a rate of 86%. Most violence committed on families was by one member at a rate of 95.6% and towards one member at a rate of 84.4%. The majority of those abused suffer from more than one form of violence, mostly smacking with the hand or hitting with the foot at a rate of 76.7%. Most cases of violence took place

within families of less than five members and with monthly incomes of less than 300 Jordanian Dinars. These families live in urban areas and most violence is carried out by males, lowly educated youth, laborers and husbands, while victims were mostly females, children and unemployed persons.

- The study of the Information and Research Center at King Hussein Foundation (2007) on women murder crimes during the period 2000-2003. It revealed a number of important results: During the study's period, 97 cases were recorded mostly occurring in 2001 at a rate of 30.9%. The number of convicted persons in the study cases was 113 and the number of victims was 104. Most of those convicted were youth between the ages of 18 and 20 (23.9%), working in the crafts field (45.7%), married (57.5%) and with school education (48.7%). Motives for murder and attempted murder were as follows: suspicion in the female victim (25.8%), family violence (25.8%), proven adultery (15.5%), prostitution (6.2%), financial disputes (6.2%), theft (5.2%) and other reasons (15.5%). Murders and attempted murders took place in the capital governorate (37.1%), Irbid (17.5%), Balqaa (13.4%), Zarqa (11.3%), Aqaba (5.2%), Karak (4.1%), Tafilah (3.1%), Maan (2.1%), Jarash (2.1%), Ajloun (2.1%), Mafrq (1%) and Madaba (1%). Crimes took place mostly in the victim's home (69%) and outside (28%). The convicted person's relationship with the victim was her brother (45.1%), husband (15%), first-degree relative (14.2%), non-relative such as neighbor or thief (10.6%), father (8.9%), acquaintances such as husband's friend or mother's friend or victim's friend (6.9%). The majority of female victims were youth between the ages of 22 and 27. They were married at a rate of 48.1% and unemployed at a rate of 58.7%.
- The Queen Zein Al Sharaf Institute for Development study (2002) concluded that the majority of women exposed to family violence are wives primarily and daughters secondarily. Causes of violence towards the wife are: the husband's drinking of alcohol, laying the responsibility of raising the children on her shoulders and then questioning and punishing her for their behavior, the distorted religious beliefs of some husbands that they have the right to punish their wives, the husband's belief that his wife is ignorant should there be a difference in educational

level between them, the husband's family's incitement against the wife, differences between the husband and his wife's family which could lead to revenge, the husband's mistrust in his wife, discrimination between wives in cases of polygamy, the husband's desire to control and limit authority, the husband's bad faith, and the effect of pornography broadcast on some foreign satellite channels on the husband. Causes of violence against the daughter are: customs and traditions that connect the family's honor to the behavior of its daughters, some wrong widespread concepts restricting girls to certain social roles that undermine many of their rights and pressures on the parents by members of their directional families.

- The study of the Family Guidance and Awareness Center (2001). It was conducted on a sample of (1194) families living in the various administrative divisions of the Zarqa Governorate. It revealed that violence takes place in the majority of these families and towards wives at a rate of 46.36% by their husbands who make them angry at times of their families' financial crises. Those wives replied to abuse against them with submission at a rate of 34.95%.
- Al Awawdah (1998) study. It was conducted on an intentional sample of 300 married women residing in the areas of Moaqar, Sahab, Hussein Camp and Amman city. Results revealed that all of those women mentioned that they suffered from various types of violence. Social violence was most widespread at a rate of 56%, with preventing the wife from working predominant at a rate of 56.8%, followed by verbal abuse at a rate of 53% with cursing predominant at a rate of 42%, health violence through preventing the wife from determining the number of children she wishes to have at a rate of 22.8%, sexual abuse (38%) with its most severe form being forcing the wife to have sex at a rate of 34.9% and physical abuse at a rate of 30% with slapping at a rate of 62.3%.
- ◆ ***Among the most recent studies evaluating the outcomes of institutional efforts to intervene in family violence in the Jordanian society are as follows:***
 - The Ratrout and al-Shneikat (2016) study on the performance level of the women protection against violence system in Jordan. It revealed the following: the level of performance of

the system under study in light of its content analysis and feedback is very poor. The level of conformity of the system under study to effective and efficient methods derived from traditional and modern scientific directions concerned with defining, interpreting, regulating and foreseeing violence against women is poor and has not exceeded 35.55%. The impact of the outcomes and results of evaluation of the studied system on planning is very large as it has led to the suggestion of a strategic framework that can be adopted, implemented, controlled and evaluated. This strategic framework suggested by the study for protecting women against violence in Jordan in light of outputs and evaluation results includes a vision saying "Jordan without Violence against Women", a mission saying "Protecting Women Against Violence Through Effective and Efficient Scientific Methods", a strategic goal saying "Lowering the rate of violence against women in Jordan from 91% in 2016 to 10% in 2030 with an annual rate of 5.78%", a key performance index stating "lowering the periodic rate of violence against women in Jordan" and executive activities including 23 distributed among political, legislative, administrative and research fields.

- The Heyasiyyat (2016) study on the reasons and forms of violence against wives in the Jordanian society. It was conducted on a sample of 155 women, who had filed official complaints against their husbands in the capital's governorate. Results revealed that most of those exposed to violence are low-income wives, the majority of women exposed to violence are married to low-income husbands and the most prevalent forms of violence are sexual, then physical and finally psychological. Among the main reasons of violence against the wife are the family's low level of income, the husband's excessive use of social communication and the intervention of the husband's family in the wife's marriage life. The Family Protection Department had a leading role in combating the problem of violence against wives, especially with the presence of legal protection offered by the department for abused women, the availability of specialists in dealing with abuse cases against women and the provision of awareness courses and guidance for abused women.

According to the above-mentioned, it is clear that the creation of the family protection system in Jordan was a result of administrative interventions primarily and legislative ones secondarily.

Despite the many efforts focused on enhancing the family protection system in Jordan, the results were not as expected. The Family Protection Department and its partners such as the ministries of interior, social development and health failed to win the King Abdullah II Award for Excellence despite the department participating in the award's seventh version in (2013/2014) and the mentioned ministries participating in the second, third, fourth, fifth, sixth and seventh versions.

- The (Ratrouf, 2009) study aimed at identifying the system programs of the Family Protection Department and their effectiveness in changing the situations of families which carried out violence against their children in Jordan. The study population consisted of all families registered as having been involved in cases of violence against their children in Amman governorate with their cases being reported to the Family Protection Department during the period from 1/1/2007 until 31/12/2007. The total number of such cases was 576. A regular random sample of 25% was extracted amounting to 144 cases. Another intentional sample of 25 workers out of a total of 70 was extracted from the various department divisions (forensic medicine, psychiatry, social services office, reception and security investigation) to find out their opinions towards possible change that can be made to the families dealt with by the Family Protection Department programs. Results showed that 42.4% of interviewees said that the department's reception procedures were average. Regarding the measurement of these people's satisfaction towards these services, around 48.6% expressed a large level of satisfaction and 38.2% expressed average levels of satisfaction. Also, 80.6% of those studied and who had carried out violence against their children said they went through a comfortable security investigation. Regarding the services of the social services office, 86.1% of those studied mentioned that they had benefited from the family and social counseling sessions, 74.4% indicated that they had acquired the right information about social upbringing methods, while 9% of the sample mentioned that their families had received repeated cash assistance

services. The study sample expressed its satisfaction towards court services, whereas, results showed that the majority of studied families did not benefit from the services of the administrative governor except that of writing obligations against abusive individuals. Regarding the psychiatric office service, results revealed that the majority of studied families did not benefit optimally from it and the levels of satisfaction of benefitting families were average to low. Regarding the forensic medicine office, it was revealed that most of the studied families did not benefit satisfactorily from its services, whereas, there was a high level of satisfaction among benefitting families. The results also revealed that the relationship between the parents of the abused child after receiving therapy the Family Protection Department was average, closer to low. In addition, the level of interaction between the members of the abused child's family after receiving the Family Protection Department's services was closer to weak. The study also revealed that the relationship of the abusive family with its extended guiding family after receiving the department's services was average closer to weak. The study revealed that there are positive correlative statistically significant relationships at significance levels of 0.01 and 0.05 between the service of enrolling the child/children in social care homes, the abused child's situation under the supervision of the behavioral supervisor pursuant to a judicial order, the abused child being subjected to a psychiatric diagnosis, the abuser being subjected to a psychiatric diagnosis, the abusive person receiving psychiatric medical treatment, the improvement of the relationship between the abused child's parents, more interaction among the family members and an improving relationship between the abusive family and its extended guiding family. The study results also revealed that the attitudes of workers in the Family Protection Department programs towards the change that could happen to families, which practiced violence against their children, was negative and pessimistic in total.

These results have led to the following recommendations: The urgent need to review the programs and services provided by the Family Protection Department to avoid danger factors surrounding violence-related families.

The introduction of a survey system revealing the level of satisfaction of sectors receiving the services towards the services provided to them through the governorate offices. Increasing levels of effective cooperation and coordination between the Department and remaining institutions concerned with family violence cases. Designing and implementing a training program to raise the effectiveness of workers, especially social and psychological ones, and to change their negative attitudes.

According to the above, it is evident that three studies dealt with the performance of the Family Protection Department. Two of these studies, Ratrouf and Shneikat (2016) and Ratrouf (2009) revealed the low level of performance of the Family Protection Department and the low levels of satisfaction of both service recipients and providers. The Heyassat (2016) study praised the role of the Family Protection Department. This indicates the absence of a state of research consensus regarding the performance of the Family Protection Department and indicates the need for further studies in this regard.

Theoretical Framework

1. *The Scientific Explanation of the Occurrence of Family Violence and its Effect on the roles and tasks of Social Specialists:*

Violence takes place in various community institutions among which is the family. It affects the vulnerable members of families according to their ages such as children and the elderly or according to their gender such as women or according to their deficit such as the disabled. Violence has many reasons interacting between each other as expressed by the introduction to the analysis of agents used by the World Health Organization. Violence, described as a problem with a social interior and health manifestations, results in its occurrence among the vulnerable members of a family due to the interaction of four factors, which are:

- Individual factors connected to the abused person such as his young age, his excessive use of alcohol, his suffering from depression or unstable personality, and his low level of education, his low income and his witnessing or suffering from violence during childhood.
- Factors related to the relationship context of the vulnerable person such as marriage problems, unstable marriage and male dominance in the family such as regarding

him the source of orders, financial problems such as low income, unemployment, debts etc., and difficulties facing the family in carrying out its remaining duties, especially raising and caring for the children.

- Community factors represented by weak community deterrents against violence and regarding it as something normal and non-punishable by law, the low income of the local community where the family lives and weak social guardianship (the man does not provide for his family).
- Social factors such as the traditional view to the relationship between males and females, where the female must be subordinate to the male as he is her guardian, leading to social norms supporting violence as a means of social regulation (World Health Organization, 2002, p 91- 124).

Based on the understanding, interpretation, regulation and forecasting by social specialists of these factors, their roles and professional tasks are formed. They cannot carry out these roles without scientific, practical and moral preparation in the field of social work or social service. Their roles in the area of family protection can be summarized as follows:

- Protecting those vulnerable or subjected to violence through effective and efficient interventions. This includes providing social awareness to a defined sector about a certain issue such as providing awareness to childcare givers about child growth, the art of dialogue with teenagers, individual counseling to a specific case such as a person preparing for marriage and group counseling to specific cases such as female survivors of violence who teach their vulnerable counterparts.
- Protecting those vulnerable or subjected to violence by diagnosing and evaluating their cases and intervening for them.
- Providing family development services to those requesting them and measuring their levels of satisfaction after receiving them. Such services target married couples and those about to get married.

The roles of social specialists stemming from their professional tasks in the area of family protection are as follows:

- Preventive tasks to stop the occurrence of family violence. This promotes human rights, takes into consideration social culture

and goes line in line with best international practices.

- Treatment tasks based on estimating danger factors in the surroundings of those vulnerable or subjected to violence, controlling them with effective and efficient interventions and managing their cases through a comprehensive method that concentrates on the victims, their families and their local communities.

The roles and tasks of social specialists can be measured pursuant to performance indexes of which the main ones are:

- The number of annual recorded cases of family violence compared to their general average.

The annual average of family violence cases in Jordan dealt with by the Family Protection Department during the period from 1998 to 2015 was 3903.83 cases. When dividing this average into two stages, it can be illustrated that the average number of cases registered at the Family Protection Department during the period 1998-2007 was 1178.7 and is lower than the number of cases registered during the period 2008-2015, which was 7310.26. This indicates the weakness or maybe absence of the preventive role of social specialists.

- The percentage of family members who admitted to population and family health surveyors of having been subjected to violence compared to those whose cases reached official authorities.

Population and family health surveys carried out in 2007 indicated that 22.2% of surveyed women had been physically or sexually abused by their husbands once. An average of 40.1% of these women were subjected to permanent and continuous abuse. Respectively, 2.5%, 0.4%, 23%, 15%, 10%, 7% and 3% of those women sought assistance from doctors, civil society institutions, mothers, fathers, sisters, the police and health specialists consecutively (Department of Statistics, 2007). Also, the number of women victims of family violence who were referred to the Wifaq Al Osari shelter during 2007 was 290. Through these statistics, it is clear that the preventive role of social specialists is weak if not totally absent.

- The number of annual family abuse cases being followed up.

The total number of family abuse cases

registered at the social services offices of the Family Protection Department in Jordan between 1997 and 2017 was 60000 cases from among which 21494 cases are still being followed up at a rate of 477 cases being followed up by each social specialist working at the social services offices. The total number of these specialists is 45 (Ministry of Social Development, 2017, p 15). This reveals the high burden on the shoulders of social service offices as shown in Table No. 2. It should also be taken into consideration that the National Framework for Family Protection against Violence (National Council for Family Affairs, 2016) failed to separate psychological services from social ones. It integrated them into one group containing the following: assessing the psychological condition of the abused and his family, conducting social studies on the abused and his family, providing family and psychological counseling services, providing victims with sheltering services, rehabilitating and integrating perpetrators, developing parental skills, managing hotlines for children, women and their families, providing social and economic empowerment services and organizing awareness campaigns.

2. The Emergence and Development of the Protection System Against Family Violence in Jordan:

The core of family protection in Jordan began in 1997 (Ministry of Social Development, 2016) which witnessed the formation of a division for family protection at the Shmeisani police station. This step resulted from a sexual offence incident against a foreign tourist and her lack of satisfaction towards the way she was treated by the officers she met at one of the Jordanian police stations⁽¹⁾. This led her to file a complaint to her country's embassy in Amman against the officers she met at the police station. This resulted in a number of consequences, most importantly, the Public Security Directorate's determination to introduce a new police unit specialized in sexual assault cases and family protection and to build the institutional capacities of that unit and its employees according to best practices derived from the British experience. The Family Protection Division dealt with 39 cases during 1997.

The division was promoted to a department in 1998. The Public Security Directorate also signed a memorandum of understanding with the Ministry of Health involving the establishment

(1) Source: An interview with some of those who worked at the Family Protection Division since its establishment in 1997.

of forensic medicine and mental health clinics at the Family Protection Department and its divisions. It also signed another memorandum of understanding with the Ministry of ⁽¹⁾ Social Development regarding the establishment of social services offices at the department and its divisions to provide social services to victims of family violence. This agreement led to the formation of 17 offices which dealt with thousands of cases to be discussed below.

The Public Security Directorate has several objectives including: working with official and unofficial bodies to reach a safe society free of crime as much as possible. To maintain the security of mothers whose dignity is preserved and are not exposed to abuse to enable them to raise a generation of decent and aware children. To protect children from all types of abuse to be able to serve their nation confidently. To raise awareness among members of the local community of the necessity to protect family members from violence and the forms of abuse children can be exposed to both within and outside of the family. To communicate with both governmental and nongovernmental organizations dealing with women, child and human rights issues to exchange experiences and points of view on all that arises in this field. To continue communicating with countries that have developed experiences in this field to acquire new practices suitable to the Jordanian society according to its traditions, customs and religious teachings. To establish a database concerned with following up, studying and analyzing new practices of dealing with such cases. The Department works on achieving its objectives through four stages: The first is to discover and report cases. The second is to immediately respond to the discovered and reported case. The third is to intervene in the conditions of the case, and the fourth is to close the case file after the individual concerned has received services (National Council for Family Affairs, p. 18, 2016).

The department works on achieving its objectives through four stages. The first is discovering and reporting cases. The second is instant response to the discovered and reported case. The third is the intervention stage into the case and the fourth is the closure of the case file after the case has received services (National Council for Family Affairs, 2016, p 18).

The National Council for Family Affairs Law No. 27 was issued in 2001 and stated the council's objective in Article 4 as being: "to enhance the status of the Jordanian family and amplify its

role in society. This shall enable it to contribute to preserving the moral and civilizational heritage of the Islamic world in line with the economic, social and cultural changes taking place in the Kingdom". To achieve this goal, the council works specifically on achieving the following: 1- Contributing to setting the development plans, policies and strategies related to the family and its members and following up their implementation. 2-Contributing to improving the family's quality of life, caring for it, enhancing its role and enabling it to meet the requirements of its members and ensure their safety. 3- Contributing to the family's advancement, protecting and maintaining its stability and preserving its cohesion and identity. 4- Supporting the efforts of various social institutions and agencies, in public and private sectors, concerned with family affairs and improving coordination and achieving integration between these parties (Ministry of Social Development, 2006). This law has led to the establishment of the National Council for Family Affairs. The council consists of a board of trustees and a technical secretariat. The Board of Trustees is chaired by Queen Rania Al Abdullah and includes representatives from the public and private sectors, whereas, the technical secretariat is directed by a secretary general and the directors connected to him.

In 2004, the Ordinance of Shelters for Family Protection (No. 48) was issued to support Article No. 4 of the Ministry of Social Affairs and Labor Law No. 14 of 1956 and its amendments (Ministry of Social Development, 2015). This ordinance and the instructions for licensing protection shelters No. 15 of 2009 issued pursuant thereto led to regulating the work of battered women's care homes amounting to three in total.

The first is Dar Al-Wifaq Osari in Amman which opened its doors in 2007. The second is the Jordanian Women's Union shelter licensed in 2012 and the third is the Dar Al-Wifaq Osari in the city of Irbid which started working in 2015.

In 2006, the National Framework for Family Protection was issued and contained a methodology for working with family violence cases (National Council for Family Affairs, 2006). The Family Protection Law No. 6 of Jordan was issued in 2008 (Ministry of Social Development, 2006). The Prevention of Human Trafficking Law No. 9 was issued in 2009. In 2015, the Dar Karama for victims of human trafficking was opened pursuant to its memorandum of association issued in 2012 and pursuant to the anti-human trafficking law.

A replacement for the 2006 National Framework for Family Protection was issued in 2016 with the same name (National Council for Family Affairs, 2016). However, it failed to name the parties concerned with its three stages, which are discovering, reporting, immediately responding and intervening, major operations (estimating danger factors, case management and case conference etc.) and the limits of soft intervention among them based on the coordination of organizational efforts and cooperative action. In 2017, a new version of the Family Protection Law of 2008 was issued for many positive reasons (Ministry of Social Development, 2016) such as the redefining of the family, ensuring obligatory reporting of cases, involving sharia judiciary, settling of family disputes and using (cctv) ⁽²⁾ technology in courts and determining judicial bodies.

Family protection was accompanied with a number of field studies aiming at understanding family violence and evaluating the results of institutional efforts for intervention. Among the most recent studies on family violence in the Jordanian society are as follows:

3. Rates and Trends of Family Protection Issues in Jordan from a Statistical Perspective:

After collecting data concerned with family protection issues in Jordan from the Family Protection Department and the Ministry of Social Development and after processing this data statistically using some descriptive statistical coefficients such as arithmetic means and time series, the following was concluded:

- The annual average of family abuse cases according to data collected between 1998 and 2015 was 39.4 cases as shown in Table No. 1. This shows that the Family Protection Department and its partners deal with an average of 4000 family abuse cases against both genders annually.
- A fluctuation in the rate of change of numbers of family abuse cases during the period from 1998 to 2015 according to the data outlined in Table No. 1, indicating that there are unknown factors other than the interventions

(2) (cctv) technology is the process of the Family Protection Department's video recording of the victim's statement to use it in court. This means that the victim's statements are taken only once during the judicial process to ensure his psychological health.

of the Family Protection Department and its partners.

Table 1.

A distribution of the numbers of family abuse cases dealt with by the Jordan Family Protection Department according to their year of registration during the period from 1998 to 2015, their arithmetic means and change rates

Year	No. of cases*	Change %**
1998	295	
1999	531	80
2000	631	18.83
2001	564	10.62
2002	661	17.19
2003	1178	78.21
2004	1423	20.79
2005	1796	26.21
2006	1764	1.78
2007	2944	66.89
2008	4312	46.46
2009	6416	48.79
2010	8605	34.11
2011	7931	7.83
2012	7874	0.71
2013	7873	0.01
2014	7606	3.39
2015	7865	3.40
Arithmetic mean**	3903.83	

*Source: Ministry of Social Development, 2016.

** Source: researcher's calculations.

Based on Table No. 2:

- The annual average of cases of family abuse against women which were referred to the Dar Wifaq Osari in Amman according to data for the years between 2007 and 2015 was 572 cases. This is shown in Table No. 3 and indicates that the Ministry of Social Development deals with an average of 572 abused women annually.
- The number of women subjected to family violence referred to the Dar Al Wifaq Osari in Amman was 8.72% of all cases dealt with by the Family Protection Department during the period between 2007 and 2015 according to Table No. 2. This indicates that a tenth of all cases dealt with by the Family Protection

Department are in need of sheltering services.

- A fluctuation in the rate of change of the numbers of family abuse cases against women who were referred to the Dar Al Wifaq Osari shelter during the period from 2007 to 2015 according to the data in Table No. 2. This indicates that there are unknown factors affecting this issue other than the interventions of the Family Protection Department and its partners.
- The annual average of children accompanying their mothers who were referred to the Dar Al Wifaq Osari shelter during the period from 2007 to 2015 was 126 male and female children as indicated in Table No. 2. This confirms that family violence contributes to the homelessness of children and their mothers.

Table 2.

Distribution of the numbers of women victims of family violence referred with their children to the Dar Al Wifaq Osari shelter in Amman in the period between 2007 and 2015, their rates out of the total numbers dealt with by the Family Protection Department, their arithmetic means and rates of change

Year	Total No. of cases*	No. of women referred to Dar Al Wifaq Osari shelter in Amman and their percentages			No. of children accompanying their mothers in Dar Al Wifaq Osari shelter
		No.	% of total	% of change of numbers of those referred to the shelter	
2007	2944	290	9.85		54
2008	4312	501	11.61	72.75	70
2009	6416	806	12.56	60.87	105
2010	8605	734	8.52	- 8.93	158
2011	7931	505	6.63	-31.19	138
2012	7874	699	8.87	38.41	165
2013	7873	615	7.81	-12.01	192
2014	7606	526	6.91	-14.47	110
2015	7865	472	6	10.26	138
Arithmetic mean	6825.11	572	8.75		125.55

* Source: Ministry of Social Development, 2016.

- The remaining data was collected and calculated by the researcher.

Based on the above, the main features of family abuse cases in Jordan can be revealed as follows:

- Cases of family violence referred to the Family Protection Department are highly fluctuant. They rise at times and fall at others. This indicates the absence of regulation through effective and efficient social interventions leading to a decrease in rates.
- Women and children are targets in family and domestic violence.
- The majority of family violence cases (88.57%) dealt with by the Family Protection Department did not receive sheltering services. This indicates that these victims received other forms of services such as socially related ones (e.g. guidance, direction and awareness raising or administrative ones such as binding guarantees and commitments).
- The rate of women subjected to family violence who enroll in Dar Al Wifaq Osari is 8.57% of the total number of cases dealt with by the Family Protection Department. This is higher than the rate of children enrolled which is 2.68%.
- Family violence results in 572 women and 126 of their children resorting to Dar Al Wifaq Osari in Amman annually.
- The nature of intervention into family violence should be therapeutic and not precautionary.

Table 3.

Trends of cases dealt with by Social Services Offices/ Family Protection from the point of view of their employees

Office	Cases Trends
Irbid	Sexual, Physical
East Amman	Sexual
Madaba	Sexual
Zarqaa	Sexual, Physical
West Amman	Sexual
Mafraq	Sexual, Physical
Rusaifa	Sexual, Physical
Amman	Sexual

*Source: Ministry of Social Development, 2017, p 15.

**Source: the researcher's calculations.

Study Methodology

1. The study used the qualitative research method, which is based on the following methods:
2. Analysis of document content method, which was used to reveal the justifications of developing social services offices at the Family Protection Department and the expected roles and responsibilities of their employees from an institutional coordination and case management perspective. The method also reveals the size of work allocated to them, growing demand on the department's services and the characteristics of those capable of receiving its services such as abused women and children. This was revealed clearly in the theoretical part of this study.

Analyzed documents can be divided in four groups as follows:

- ◆ Legislative scope consisting of the following documents: Constitution of Jordan 1952 and its amendments until 2015, the Law of the Ministry of Social Affairs No (14) for 1956, National Council for Family affairs Law 27 of 2001, the Protection from Domestic Violence Law 6 of 2008, Law No. 9 of 2009 on the Prevention of Human Trafficking, Juvenile Law No. 32 of 2014, the Family Protection Regulation No. 48 of 2008, the Bylaw of Licensing and Managing Child Shelters of 2009, the bylaw of Sheltering Victims of Human Trafficking No. 30 of 2012, and the Instructions on Licensing Women's Protection Homes of 2009.
 - ◆ The Planning Scope consisting of the following documents: The National Framework for Family Protection of 2006, Jordan Vision 2015, the National Framework for Family Protection 2016, and the Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Social Development, 2017- 2021.
 - ◆ Statistical Scope consisting of statistical reports of social services offices at the Family Protection Department from 1997 to 2017.
 - ◆ Research Scope consisting of previous studies reports.
3. Semi-structured Interviews of both individual and group types: They were used with some employees of social services offices and those concerned with their technical affairs to examine the obstacles facing these offices

and the trends of their services' recipients. This method included two open questions: what are the obstacles facing your offices' work? Which sectors receive the largest amounts of services from your offices?

4. **Brainstorming Method:** It was split into three stages, the first estimating the training requirements of social services offices employees and their expectations from the Ministry of Social Development. The second stage was used to raise questions arising from the respondents' responses and included many open questions such as: Why do your offices face the obstacles you mentioned earlier? Why are your offices' services in greater demand by the family sectors you mentioned earlier more than other sectors? Since you mentioned your training requirements, why has the Ministry of Social Development not met these requirements? Since you mentioned your expectations from the Ministry of Social Development, do you believe that your ministry will confront the obstacles facing your offices' work? The third stage was used to reveal the consensus of the respondents to the answers of the questions raised according to the "Delphi Technique".
5. **Focus Working Groups:** They consisted of two groups, the first including the heads of social services offices and the second including those concerned with the technical affairs of social services offices from the Ministry of Social Development. The questions asked to the two groups were the same as those of the interview and brainstorming methods mentioned above.

The study collected its data and information for its second research method (interviews), the third method (brainstorming) and the fourth method (focus working groups) from a deliberate sample of those concerned with social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions in the Jordanian governorates. Their characteristics are shown in Table 1. The number of this sample was 11 male and female employees of social services offices and those concerned with their technical affairs. Those individuals were divided into two groups. The first group includes heads of social services offices in North Amman, Family Protection Department Headquarters, Balqaa, Madaba, East amman, Irbid, Al Mafraq and Al Rusayfah. There were eight employees

comprising 47% of the total number of heads of social services offices at the Family protection Department and its division. They also comprised 18% of the total number of employees working at social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions, which are 45 male and female employees. The second group consists of three employees concerned with the technical affairs of social services offices. They include the Director of the Directorate of Juvenile Care and Societal Security, the Head of the Protection Division at the Ministry of Social Development, and the Director of Al Rusayfah Girls Care Home.

Table 4.

Characteristics of Study Sample Members

Characteristic	Level	Repetition	%
Gender	Males	9	82
	Females	3	18
	Total	11	100
Education Level	BA	11	100
	Total	11	100
	Sociology	6	54.54
Academic Specialization	Special Education	2	18.18
	Law	1	9.1
	Education and Psychology	2	18.18
	Total	11	100
Type of Job	First	11	100
	Total	11	100
	Directorate Manager	1	9.09
Job Title	Head of Division in Directorate	1	9.09
	Head of Social Services Office	8	72.72
	Homecare Director	1	9.09
	Total	11	100
Place of Work	Capital Governorate 5	5	45.45
	Zarqaa Governorate 2	2	18.18
	Mafraq Governorate 1	1	9.09
	Balqa Governorate 1	1	9.09
	Irbid Governorate 1	1	9.09
	Madaba Governorate 1	1	9.09
Total	11	100	

Study Results, Conclusions, Recommendations and Suggestions

A. Study Results:

To answer the study's first sub-question, the interview method was used with some of those concerned with social services offices such as employees and those following up their technical affairs. Results revealed that social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions face 20 obstacles from the point of view of some of their employees and those concerned with their technical affairs such as officials from the Ministry of Social Development. These obstacles are as follows:

1. The vagueness of the professional roles of social workers such as case diagnosis, evaluation, intervention and follow up.
2. The marginalization of social workers by administrative officers upon conducting case conferences.
3. The absence of a technical reference for social services offices at the Ministry of Social Development headquarters between the directorates of juvenile care and family care.
4. The overlap of powers and responsibilities between partner bodies and the dissatisfaction of office workers as a result. For example, administrative officers in social services centers (who are of a security background) interfere with the role of social workers appointed by the Ministry of Social Development leading to ambiguous roles. Security officers do not inform social workers working with them in the offices about cases referred to the courts. They also ask them to arrange commitment instruments to be signed by offenders (such as husbands who abuse their wives). Most of these officers lack scientific, practical and moral preparation in the field of social work and have job titles as social workers even though they report to their majors at security departments and not to the managers of the social services centers in which they work.
5. The large numbers of files open for follow up. Child cases have reached around 20,000 and following them up is difficult due to lack of transportation. Women cases also lack high valuing.
6. The absence of danger factor evaluation standards for cases in general and sexual abuse cases in particular before, during and after their victims are referred to care homes.
7. The absence of (legal) release criteria for cases from care homes, especially cases of sexual abuse.
8. The out-dated case study form used currently and the difficulty in developing decisions based on its results, It also contains a check box for the police officer's decision.
9. The difficulty of referring or hosting victims of violence in care homes, especially sexually assaulted girls, after the legal adaptation of their cases by public prosecutors. The reasons behind this difficulty are the technical directorates at the ministry headquarters on one hand and the late arrival of some cases to the social services offices due to prolonged police procedures on the other hand.
10. The absence of technical orientation of social workers by the concerned parties at the ministry headquarters.
11. The dependence on some office directors as behavioral supervisors. This could increase their workloads and sometimes prevent them from following up registered cases.
12. The absence of work descriptions for social workers and the lack of awareness of the importance of such job description cards during their work.
13. The absence of clear procedures (procedural guide) for dealing with cases upon their diagnosis and during intervention. These procedures can also be misused during internal or external implementation (social services offices and partners from within the Ministry of Social Development and beyond).
14. The case files' lack of data and information upon transferring cases from one administrative unit to another such as transferring them from social services offices to shelters. This weakens the process of making decisions and implementing them.
15. Lack of engagement of social workers working in social services offices by the officers of the Family Protection Department in case study conferences. Also, the characteristics of the case conference directors lack professionalism and workers

lack awareness of the mechanisms related to the conducting of a case conference, its time and venue.

16. Threats by some ministry directors to some workers in social services offices of being moved to other departments. This leads to poor job security, which is amplified by their psychological sufferings and lack of allowances such as those granted to their counterparts in other administrative departments.
17. The unclear lines between authorities and responsibilities between the family and juvenile care directorates at the level of difficult cases worthy of entering care homes. Each of the two directorates throws the ball in the other's court leading to the humiliation of the social workers in front of the police officers of the Family Protection Department.
18. The absence of a computerized system to follow up and evaluate cases and the absence of electronic communication between social services offices and their partners from within and outside the Ministry of Social Development.
19. Poor resources such as lack of means of transportation (cars), small buildings and lack of supplies.
20. Increasing demand for the offices' services and the complexity of cases needing intervention.

These obstacles can be treated through the Ministry of Social Development's approach of adopting a policy of approving social services offices and controlling the quality of their services. This depends on the enactment of the Jordanian Social Work Law, which was mentioned as one of the initiatives of the Jordan 2025 Vision.

Accordingly, the study has answered its first sub-question by illustrating that social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions face 20 obstacles from the point of view of some of their employees and those from the Ministry of Social Development concerned with their technical affairs. Such obstacles could be overcome through approving an institutional approval method and quality control of services.

To answer the study's second sub-question, the interview method was used with a number of experienced employees at the social services

offices and those following their technical affairs. Results reveal that the social services office at the Family Protection Department deals with two or more cases of sexually assaulted girls daily and that the remaining offices deal with categories shown in the following table. This calls for developing the knowledge, skills and trends of these offices' employees.

Therefore, the study has answered its second sub-question by saying that social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions provide their services to both physically and sexually assaulted cases from the point of view of some of their employees and those from the Ministry of Social Development concerned with their technical affairs.

To answer the study's third question, the brainstorming method was used with some of those concerned with social services offices including employees and followers of their technical affairs. The study results reveal that there are eight training requirements for social workers at the social services offices, which could be met through continuous education programs implemented by the Ministry of Social Development and its partners. The requirements are as follows:

- ◆ Practical applications of legislations related to protection such as the juvenile law.
- ◆ Psychosocial evaluation of cases.
- ◆ Altering behavior of juveniles and behavioral treatment.
- ◆ Conducting deep interviews with cases, especially girls cases
- ◆ Body-language communication.
- ◆ Dealing with indicators of mental illnesses such as suicide tendencies and depression.
- ◆ Measurements for calculating danger factors for cases and their practical applications.
- ◇ Case management through the participation method.

Therefore, the study has answered its third sub-question by saying that there are eight training requirements for social workers at social services offices. These requirements need to be met by the Ministry of Social Development through an effective and efficient training program.

To answer the study's fourth sub-question, the brainstorming method was used with some of those concerned with social services offices such as workers and followers of technical affairs. Results revealed that workers at the social services

offices anticipate from the Ministry of Social Development to carry out seven things that reflect their aspirations as follows:

- To receive bonuses the same as their colleagues in other administrative departments.
- An evaluation of the danger factors surrounding the employee.
- Securing necessary work requirements such as means of transportation.
- Senior employees meeting workers at the social services offices.
- Providing separate buildings other than those of the Public Security Departments.
- Justice to the employees in light of the results of their efforts.
- Concerned bodies carrying out their roles in the area of family counseling and guidance.

Accordingly, the study has answered its fourth sub-question by saying that there are seven expectations (aspirations) for social workers at social services offices, which must be adopted by the Ministry of Social Development.

Based on the study's answers to its four sub-questions, it has answered its main question by saying the following: the social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions face 20 obstacles, provide their services to sexually and physically assaulted cases, have eight training requirements for their employees and their workers have seven expectations from the Ministry of Social Development.

B. Study Conclusions:

1. The large number of technical and administrative obstacles facing social services offices at the Family Protection Department and its divisions indicating the failure of the National Framework for Family Protection against Violence of 2007 and its 2016 counterpart in eliminating them.
2. The complexity of the cases receiving the services of the social services offices at the Family Protection Department.
3. The large number of training requirements of social workers in the area of family protection and the absence of parties who measure and meet them.
4. The large expectations of social workers from the Ministry of Social Development in the form of administrative problems and the

absence of those who can solve them.

E. Study Recommendations:

1. To develop the National Framework for Family Protection against Violence to include setting the roles and tasks of concerned institutions and those working for them.
2. To professionalize Jordanian social work according to the initiative outlined in the Jordan Vision 2025.

C. Study Suggestions:

1. Establishing a family protection directorate at the Ministry of Social Development.
2. The human resources directorate at the Ministry of Social Development should provide job descriptions for workers at social services offices/ social protection in the form of cards.
3. The National Council for Family Affairs should modernize the National Framework for Family Protection against Violence in light of the experiences of field workers and the framework should contain clear items in the area of evaluation of danger factors and indicators.
4. The Legal Affairs Unit at the Ministry of Social Development should prepare a procedural guide for child protection cases inspired by the Juvenile Law.
5. Lines should be drawn between the authorities and responsibilities of the Public Security Directorate and the Ministry of Social Development regarding their dealing with cases subjected to violence in accordance with the role expected from each of them and in light of legislations and the operation management method.
6. The National Council for Family Affairs should determine the requirements of conducting a case conference and the characteristics of those participating in such conferences and those managing them.
7. The Directorate of Social Societies Development at the Ministry of Social Development should establish a database for social services offices and their internal and external partners.
8. Objective standards should be set for the follow up of open cases.

9. Bonuses for employees of social services offices should be based on their tasks and volumes of work.

up by 17 Social Services Offices (Unpublished Report).

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